

A Hybrid-Bessel Operational Matrix Approach for Solving a System of High Order Linear Volterra Integro-Differential Equations

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ABSTRACT

In this article, approximate solutions of linear Volterra Integro-Differential equations system with variable coefficients types by means of the hybrid-Bessel method is considered. We use the transfer matrix from Bessel-hybrid functions to Taylor polynomials, to obtain the operational matrixes and approximation of functions. The matrix equations correspond to a system of linear algebraic equations with the unknown Bessel-hybrid coefficients. Some examples are given, showing its effectiveness and convenience.

KEYWORDS: Bessel-hybrid functions, Volterra, System of integro-differential equations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Integro-differential and integral equations system have been found to various kinds of phenomena in science and engineering, such as glass-forming process, nano-hydrodynamics, drop wise condensation, and wind ripple in the desert (Bo et al., 2007), (Sun et al., 2007), (Wang et al., 2007), (Xu et al., 2007). Many researchers are shown in solving such types of integro-differential equations system, in (Yusufoglu, 2008) has used homotopy perturbation algorithm to solve a system of Fredholm-Volterra type integral equations. Linear IDEs system has been solved in (Maleknejad et al., 2004) by using Galerkin methods with the hybrid Legendre and block-pluse functions on interval $[0, 1)$. (Biazar et al. 2009) by Homotopy perturbation method solved systems of integro-differential equations, in (Pour-Mahmoud et al. 2005) presented the Tau method for the numerical solution of systems of Fredholm integro-differential equations. Authors in (Rashidinia, 2012) have used Taylor series method for the system of linear Volterra integro-differential equations. Yalcynbas in (Yalcynbas, 2013) solved linear Fredholm integral equations system with variable coefficients. Also, readers who are interested in learning more about this topic, could refer to (Yusufoglu, 2007), (Biazar, 2005), (Yuzbasi, 2015), (SHEN, 2007), (Yuzbasi et al., 2011).

In this research we try to introduce a solution of system of linear Volterra integro-differential equations the following form:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^r p_{ij}^k(x) y_j^{(k)}(x) = g_i(x) + \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{ij}^v \int_a^x k_{ij}^v(x,t) y_j(t) dt, \quad (1)$$

$$0 \leq a \leq x, t \leq b, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r,$$

under the mixed conditions

$$y_j^{(k)}(a) = y_{ik}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1.$$

where $y_j(t)$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, r$ are an unknown functions, the known functions are $p_{ij}^k(x)$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, n$, $g_i(x)$, $k_{ij}^v(x,t)$, $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Also, ξ_{ij}^v and y_{ik} , $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$ are real or complex constants.

The paper is organized as follows:

- In Section 2, we express some necessary basic properties of Bessel-hybrid functions and Taylor polynomials.
- In Section 3, we introduce the fundamental relations and method of solution.
- In Section 4, we report results of some problems which are solved by propose method.

2 PROPERTIES OF BESSEL-HYBRID FUNCTIONS AND TAYLOR POLYNOMIALS

2.1 Bessel-hybrid functions

Bessel-hybrid functions $b(n, m, x)$ have three arguments n , m and x . Respectively, n is the order for block-pulse, m is the order for Bessel polynomials and x is the normalized time, is defined on the interval $[0, 1)$ as (Ordokhani et al., 2015):

$$b(n, m, x) = \begin{cases} J_{m,M}(Nx - n + 1), & \frac{n-1}{N} \leq x < \frac{n}{N}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $J_{m,M}(x)$ truncated Bessel polynomials of first kind which are defined, the m -th degree truncated Bessel polynomial of first kind by

$$J_{m,M}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{M-m}{2} \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!(k+m)!} \left(\frac{x}{2}\right)^{2k+m}, \quad 0 \leq x < \infty, \quad m \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (3)$$

In (Ordokhani et al., 2014), M is positive integer, so that $M \geq m$, $m = 0, 1, \dots, M$ and a set of block-pulse functions $\varphi_i(x)$,

$i = 1, \dots, N$, on the interval $L^2[0, 1]$ is defined in (Hong Yang et al., 2012).

2.2 Transformation matrix basis and function approximation

Now, we can expanded a function $y_j(x)$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, r$, in $L^2(0, 1)$ space in Bessel-hybrid functions as

$$y_j(x) \simeq A_j^T B(x) = B^T(x) A_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r, \quad (4)$$

where

$$A_j = [a_{10}^j, \dots, a_{1M}^j, \dots, a_{N0}^j, \dots, a_{NM}^j]^T,$$

$$B(x) = [b(1,0,x), \dots, b(1,M,x), \dots, b(N,0,x), \dots, b(N,M,x)]^T.$$

where A_j and $B(x)$ are constant coefficients and basis vectors of Bessel-hybrid functions. Also, we can transform the Bessel-hybrid functions to M-th degree Taylor basis functions. In matrix form as (Ordokhani et al., 2015):

$$B(x) = D\hat{X}(x), \quad (5)$$

$\hat{X}(x)$ is Taylor polynomials defined in N subinterval of $[0, 1)$, where defined in (Ordokhani et al., 2015). By substituting Eq. (5) in Eq. (4), we get

$$y_j(x) \simeq A_j^T D\hat{X}(x) = \hat{X}^T(x) D^T A_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r. \quad (6)$$

2.3 Operational matrix of Taylor polynomials

We want to present dual operational matrix of $\hat{X}(x)$ with taking the integration of the cross product of two Taylor polynomials function vectors in subinterval $[\frac{i-1}{N}, \frac{i}{N})$, $i = 1, \dots, N$, of $[0, 1)$ is obtain:

$$\hat{H}_f = \int_a^b \hat{X}(t) \hat{X}^T(t) dt, \quad (9)$$

as defined in more detail in the (Ordokhani et al., 2015). Finally, we obtain operational matrix of derivative for $\hat{X}(x)$ as

$$\hat{X}^{(k)}(x) = (\hat{B})^k \hat{X}(x), \quad (10)$$

where

$$\hat{B} = \begin{cases} \text{diag}(B^T, O, \dots, O), & 0 \leq x < \frac{1}{N}, \\ \text{diag}(O, B^T, \dots, O), & \frac{1}{N} \leq x < \frac{2}{N}, \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \text{diag}(O, O, \dots, B^T), & \frac{N-1}{N} \leq x < 1, \end{cases}$$

B is operational matrix of derivative for Taylor polynomials in $[0, 1)$, which is defined in (Yuzbasi et al., 2012).

3 FUNDAMENTAL RELATIONS AND SOLUTION METHOD

3.1 Matrix relation for the differential part

In this section we obtain approximation to the k-th derivative of $y_j(x)$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, r$, by using Eqs. (6) and (10), we have

$$y_j^{(k)}(x) \simeq (\hat{X}^{(k)}(x))^T D^T A_j = \hat{X}^T(x)(\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r. \quad (11)$$

According to Eq. (11), we have matrix form of differential part as

$$E_i(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^r p_{ij}^k(x) y_j^{(k)}(x) \simeq \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^r p_{ij}^k(x) \hat{X}^T(x) (\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j, \quad (12)$$

by using nodal points of Newton-Cotes as (Yuzbasi et al., 2012)

$$x_s = \frac{2s-1}{2N(M+1)}, \quad s = 1, 2, \dots, N(M+1). \quad (13)$$

We have

$$E_i(x_s) \simeq \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^r p_{ij}^k(x_s) \hat{X}^T(x_s) (\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r,$$

or in general

$$EA = \sum_{k=0}^n P_k \bar{X} (\bar{B})^k \bar{D} A, \quad (14)$$

where

$$A = [A_1, A_2, \dots, A_r]^T, \quad P^k(x) = [p_{ij}^k(x)], \quad ij = 1, 2, \dots, r,$$

$$P_k = \text{diag}(P^k(x_1), P^k(x_2), \dots, P^k(x_{N(M+1)})),$$

$$\bar{B} = \text{diag}(\hat{B}^T, \hat{B}^T, \dots, \hat{B}^T), \quad \bar{D} = \text{diag}(\hat{D}^T, \hat{D}^T, \dots, \hat{D}^T),$$

$$\bar{X} = \text{diag}(\hat{X}^T(x_1), \hat{X}^T(x_2), \dots, \hat{X}^T(x_{N(M+1)})).$$

3.2 Matrix relation for the Volterra integral part

We can write kernel function $k_{ij}^v(x, t)$ approximated by truncated Maclaurin series and truncated Bessel-hybrid series, so matrix form as

$$k_{ij}^v(x, t) = \hat{X}^T(x)_i k_{ij}^v \hat{X}(t), \quad (15)$$

$$k_{ij}^v(x, t) = B^T(x)_b k_{ij}^v B(t), \quad (16)$$

where ${}_i k_{ij}^v$ is defined in (Ordokhani et al., 2015). By substituting Eq. (5) in Eq. (16) and putting equal to Eq. (15), we obtain:

$${}_b k_{ij}^v = (D^T)^{-1} {}_i k_{ij}^v (D)^{-1}.$$

Moreover, by substituting the matrix form of Eqs. (4) and (16) in Volterra integral part of Eq. (1), we have

$$\sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{ij}^v \int_a^x k_{ij}^v(x,t) y_j(t) dt \simeq \sum_{j=1}^r \int_a^x B^T(x)_b k_{ij}^{\xi_v} B(t) B^T(t) A_j dt = \sum_{j=1}^r B^T(x)_b k_{ij}^{\xi_v} Q_v(x) A_j, \quad (17)$$

so that $Q_v(x) = D \hat{H}_v(x) D^T$, where $\hat{H}_v(x)$ the integration of dual operational matrix of Taylor polynomials in N subinterval of $[0, 1]$, is defined in (Ordokhani et al., 2015). Hence, we have matrix form of Volterra integral part, if take Eq. (5) into Eq. (17)

$$V_i(x) = \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{ij}^v \int_a^x k_{ij}^v(x,t) y_j(t) dt \simeq \sum_{j=1}^r \hat{X}^T(x) M \hat{H}_v(x) D^T A_j, \quad M = D^T_b k_{ij}^{\xi_v} D, \quad (18)$$

By placing in Eq. (18) the collocation points defined in Eq. (13) as

$$V_i(x_s) = \sum_{j=1}^r \hat{X}^T(x_s) M \hat{H}_v(x_s) D^T A_j, \quad M = D^T_b k_{ij}^{\xi_v} D.$$

Finally, we obtain

$$VA = \overline{\overline{X}} \overline{\overline{M}} \overline{\overline{H}}_v \overline{\overline{D}} A, \quad (19)$$

where

$$\overline{\overline{M}} = \text{diag}(M, M, \dots, M), \quad \overline{\overline{H}}_v = \text{diag}(\hat{H}_v(x_1), \hat{H}_v(x_2), \dots, \hat{H}_v(x_{N(M+1)})).$$

3.3 Method of solution

To solve Eq. (1) with conditions, we substituting Eqs. (14) and (19) in Eq. (1) as

$$EA = G + VA, \quad (20)$$

where,

$$G = [g_1(x_s), g_2(x_s), \dots, g_r(x_s)]^T, \quad s = 1, 2, \dots, N(M+1),$$

and EA, FA, VA are including vector A , is unknown. So we have

$$(E - V)A = G, \quad (21)$$

or, we have fundamental matrix equations as

$$WA = G, \quad W = E - V. \quad (22)$$

Now, we used Eq. (11) to obtain the matrix form of initial conditions, so that

$$\hat{X}^T(a) (\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j = y_{ik}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (23)$$

or briefly,

$$\overline{\overline{X}}_a \overline{\overline{B}} \overline{\overline{D}} A = Y_k, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\overline{\overline{X}}_a = \text{diag}(\hat{X}^T(a), \hat{X}^T(a), \dots, \hat{X}^T(a)).$$

Consequently, we can write the fundamental matrix equations for initial conditions as

$$U_k A = Y_k, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (25)$$

where

$$U_k = \overline{X}_a \overline{B} \overline{D}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1,$$

$$Y_k = [y_{1k}, y_{2k}, \dots, y_{rk}]^T.$$

Ultimately, we are replacing the rows of U_k by last rows of W and the rows of Y_k by last rows of G to obtain the solution of Eq. (1) under conditions

$$\hat{W}A = \hat{G}, \quad (26)$$

where

$$[\hat{W} | \hat{G}] = \begin{bmatrix} W & \vdots & G \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ U_k & \vdots & Y_k \end{bmatrix},$$

We obtain A from system of Eq. (26) and with substituting A in Eq. (4), we get approximate solution of Eq. (1).

4 ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

The aim of this method is to obtain an approximate solution to the problem with minimum errors, we report the results of some examples given in the different papers. In addition, express absolute error function which is defined as

$$E(y_j) = |y_j(x) - y_{jN}(x)|,$$

where $y_j(x)$ is the exact solution of Eq. (1) and $y_{jN}(x)$ is the approximate of $y_j(x)$. All the examples were performed on the computer by means of a program written in MATLAB.

Example 4.1. Consider system of the linear VIE (Hong Yang et al., 2012)

$$\begin{cases} 2xy_1(x) + xy_2(x) = 2x + \int_0^x (3ty_1(t) + (2x+1)y_2(t))dt, \\ xy_1(x) - 2xy_2(x) = x - \frac{5x^3}{3} + \frac{7x^4}{6} + \int_0^x (2(t+x)y_1(t) + (2x+t)y_2(t))dt, \end{cases}$$

The exact solutions are $y_1(x) = x+1$ and $y_2(x) = -x$. Now, for $N = 2$, $M = 2$, according to the proposed method, we obtain the exact solution.

Example 4.2. Consider the following system of the linear VIE (SHEN, 2007)

$$\begin{cases} y_1(x) = \cosh(x) + x \sin(x) - \int_0^x \exp(-(t-x))y_1(t)dt - \int_0^x \cos(t-x)y_2(t)dt, \\ y_2(x) = 2 \sin(x) + x(\sin^2(x) + \exp(x)) - \int_0^x \exp(x+t)y_1(t)dt - \int_0^x x \cos(t)y_2(t)dt, \end{cases}$$

with the exact solutions $y_1(x) = \exp(-x)$ and $y_2(x) = 2 \sin(x)$. Absolute errors for different N and M are given in Table 1, Table 2, which shows that the error in the solutions for our method decreases by increasing the values of N, M.

Table 1 Absolute errors for $y_1(x)$ of Example 4.2.

x	Present method E(y ₁)				Method of SHEN, 2007
	N=4, M=4	N=4, M=6	N=3, M=8	N=3, M=10	
0	0	0	0	0	8.88×10^{-16}
0.1	2.03×10^{-4}	3.98×10^{-7}	1.25×10^{-9}	1.15×10^{-12}	2.32×10^{-8}
0.2	1.04×10^{-4}	1.59×10^{-7}	5.13×10^{-10}	7.28×10^{-13}	1.91×10^{-6}
0.3	5.97×10^{-5}	5.28×10^{-9}	6.45×10^{-9}	1.33×10^{-12}	2.83×10^{-5}
0.4	1.63×10^{-4}	1.48×10^{-6}	2.23×10^{-8}	3.72×10^{-12}	2.06×10^{-4}
0.5	1.93×10^{-4}	3.27×10^{-6}	5.99×10^{-8}	4.31×10^{-12}	1.02×10^{-3}
0.6	2.59×10^{-4}	3.40×10^{-6}	3.63×10^{-8}	1.90×10^{-11}	-
0.7	5.99×10^{-4}	8.63×10^{-7}	7.63×10^{-8}	4.84×10^{-11}	-
0.8	1.58×10^{-3}	1.51×10^{-6}	2.44×10^{-7}	3.53×10^{-11}	-
0.9	3.72×10^{-3}	6.92×10^{-6}	5.90×10^{-7}	1.03×10^{-9}	-
1	7.68×10^{-3}	4.96×10^{-5}	2.07×10^{-6}	6.97×10^{-9}	-

Table 2 Absolute errors for $y_2(x)$ of Example 4.2.

x	Present method E(y ₂)				Method of SHEN, 2007
	N=4, M=4	N=4, M=6	N=3, M=8	N=3, M=10	
0	4.00×10^{-20}	5.00×10^{-22}	7.00×10^{-24}	1.26×10^{-27}	4.78×10^{-16}
0.1	5.07×10^{-5}	1.23×10^{-6}	3.02×10^{-8}	3.62×10^{-12}	1.70×10^{-8}
0.2	1.38×10^{-4}	1.69×10^{-6}	1.89×10^{-8}	2.69×10^{-12}	1.66×10^{-6}
0.3	2.13×10^{-4}	1.21×10^{-6}	2.91×10^{-8}	2.27×10^{-12}	2.87×10^{-5}
0.4	2.90×10^{-4}	1.00×10^{-7}	3.99×10^{-8}	7.69×10^{-12}	2.43×10^{-4}
0.5	4.26×10^{-4}	2.15×10^{-6}	5.55×10^{-8}	1.94×10^{-11}	1.38×10^{-3}
0.6	7.04×10^{-4}	6.04×10^{-6}	1.16×10^{-7}	7.12×10^{-11}	-
0.7	1.21×10^{-3}	1.62×10^{-7}	2.95×10^{-7}	3.94×10^{-10}	-
0.8	2.02×10^{-3}	4.39×10^{-5}	5.92×10^{-7}	1.92×10^{-9}	-
0.9	3.20×10^{-3}	1.12×10^{-4}	9.93×10^{-7}	8.16×10^{-9}	-
1	4.74×10^{-3}	2.61×10^{-4}	2.26×10^{-6}	3.12×10^{-8}	-

Example 4.3. Consider system of the linear VIDE (Yusufoglu, 2007), (Biazar, 2005), (Yuzbasi, 2015)

$$\begin{cases} y_1'(x) + y_2(x) = 1 + x + x^2 - \int_0^x (y_1(t) + y_2(t))dt, \\ y_2'(x) - y_1(x) = -1 - x + \int_0^x (-y_1(t) + y_2(t))dt, \end{cases}$$

with conditions $y_1(0) = 1$ and $y_2(0) = -1$, which the exact solutions of this system are $y_1(x) = x + \exp(x)$ and $y_2(x) = x - \exp(x)$. Table 3, Table 4 shows the absolute error of present method with results of other methods.

Table 3 Absolute errors for $y_1(x)$ of Example 4.3.

x	Present method E(y_1)		Method of Yusufoglu, 2007	Method of Biazar, 2005	Method of Yuzbasi, 2015, M=7
	N=2, M=3	N=2, M=7			
0	2.34×10^{-2}	0	0	0	0
0.2	1.24×10^{-2}	1.14×10^{-10}	3.00×10^{-9}	3.00×10^{-9}	3.05×10^{-9}
0.4	6.84×10^{-3}	1.12×10^{-10}	3.20×10^{-7}	3.20×10^{-7}	3.27×10^{-9}
0.6	1.01×10^{-2}	2.11×10^{-10}	5.36×10^{-6}	5.36×10^{-6}	3.11×10^{-9}
0.8	2.35×10^{-2}	5.03×10^{-10}	3.90×10^{-5}	3.90×10^{-5}	2.43×10^{-9}
1	4.51×10^{-2}	1.18×10^{-10}	1.79×10^{-4}	1.79×10^{-4}	8.48×10^{-9}

Table 4 Absolute errors for $y_2(x)$ of Example 4.3.

x	Present method E(y_2)		Method of Yusufoglu, 2007	Method of Biazar, 2005	Method of Yuzbasi, 2015, M=7
	N=2, M=3	N=2, M=7			
0	3.84×10^{-3}	0	0	0	0
0.2	4.03×10^{-3}	1.13×10^{-10}	2.00×10^{-9}	2.00×10^{-9}	2.06×10^{-9}
0.4	6.35×10^{-3}	1.76×10^{-10}	3.20×10^{-7}	3.20×10^{-7}	1.68×10^{-9}
0.6	1.19×10^{-2}	5.54×10^{-10}	5.35×10^{-6}	5.35×10^{-6}	1.14×10^{-9}
0.8	1.93×10^{-2}	1.44×10^{-9}	3.90×10^{-5}	3.90×10^{-5}	2.00×10^{-10}
1	2.45×10^{-2}	3.84×10^{-9}	1.79×10^{-4}	1.79×10^{-4}	8.87×10^{-8}

5 CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this paper is to develop hybrid-Bessel method for obtaining the solutions of linear systems of VIDEs. One significant advantage of this method is that with the increasing values of N and M, approximate solution is convergent and the accuracy is increased sufficiently. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate that the method is a very effective and useful technique for finding approximate solutions of these systems.

REFERENCES

T. L. Bo, L. Xie and X.J. Zheng (2007). Numerical approach to wind ripple in desert. Int. J. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul, 8, 2, 223-228.

- J. Biazar, H. Ghazvini, M. Eslami (2009). Hes Homotopy perturbation method for systems of integro-differential Equations. *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, 39, 3, 1253-1258.
- J. Biazar (2005). Solution of systems of integral-differential equations by Adomian decomposition method. *Appl. Math. Comput*, 168, 1232-1238.
- L. Hong Yang, J. Hong Shen and Y. Wang (2012). The reproducing kernel method for solving the system of the linear Volterra integral equations with variable coefficients. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 236, 2398-2405.
- K. Maleknejad and M. Tavassoli Kajani (2004). Solving linear integro-differential equation system by Galerkin methods with hybrid functions. *Appl. Math. Comput*, 159, 603-612.
- K. Maleknejad and Y. Mahmoudi (2003). Taylor polynomial solution of high-order nonlinear Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential equations. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 145, 641-653.
- Y. Ordokhani and H. Dehestani (2015). Application of the Bessel-hybrid functions for the linear Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations. *Romanian Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 5, 2, 164-177.
- Y. Ordokhani and H. Dehestani (2014). Numerical solution of the nonlinear Fredholm-Volterra Hammerstein integral equations via Bessel functions. *Journal of Information and Computing Science*, 9, 2, 123-131.
- J. Pour-Mahmoud, M.Y. Rahimi-Ardabili and S. Shahmorad (2005). Numerical solution of the system of Fredholm integro-differential equations by the Tau method. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 168, 3, 465-478.
- J. Rashidinia and A. Tahmasebi (2012). Taylor series method for the system of linear Volterra integro-differential equations. *The Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 4, 3, 331-343.
- F.Z. Sun, M. Gao, S.H. Lei, Y. B. Zhao, K. Wang, Y. T. Shi and N. H. Wang (2007). The fractal dimension of the fractal model of drop-wise condensation and its experimental study. *Int. J. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul*, 8, 2, 211-222.
- S. SHEN (2007). Application of homotopy perturbation method to the fifth-order boundary value problems. *Int. J. Contemp. Math. Sci*, 2, 1227-1236.
- H. Wang, H. M. Fu, H .F. Zhang and Z. Q. Hu (2007). A practical thermodynamic method to calculate the best glass-forming composition for bulk metallic glasses. *Int. J. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul*, 8, 2, 171-178.
- L. Xu, J.H. He and Y. Liu (2007). Electro spun nano-porous spheres with Chinese drug. *Int. J. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul*, 8, 2, 199-202.
- S. Yalcynbas (2013). Approximate solutions of linear Fredholm integral equations system with variable coefficients. *Mathematical and Computational Applications*, 18, 1 19-29.
- E. Yusufoglu (2008). A homotopy perturbation algorithm to solve a system of Fredholm-Volterra type integral equations. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 47, 1099-1107.
- E. Yusufoglu (2007). An efficient algorithm for solving integro-differential equations system. *Appl. Math. Comput*, 192, 51-55.

S. Yuzbasi (2015). Numerical solutions of system of linear Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations by the Bessel collocation method and error estimation. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 250, 320-338.

S. Yuzbasi, N. Sahin and M. Sezer (2011). Numerical solutions of systems of linear Fredholm integro-differential equations with Bessel polynomial bases. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications*, 61, 3079-3096.

S. Yuzbasi, N. Sahin and A. Yildirim (2012). A collocation approach for solving high-order linear Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 55, 547-563.